

What Qualitative Data would do to Machine Learning Pipelines

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Positionality Statement

PhD Candidate in Computer Science

Background in Clinical Neuropsychology, Statistical Science

Recently started learning about reflexivity, positionality, situated knowledge –> mainly in the context of Conversation Analysis

Running Example

Figure: Toy Example Activity Recognition

Goal: Reducing Search Space

Figure: Empty Searchspace

Goal: Reducing Search Space

Figure: Searchspace with equally distributed labels

Goal: Reducing Search Space

Figure: Searchspace with adjusted distributions

Epistemic Considerations

Pipeline

Sensor Data

+

Extracted Probabilities from Diaries

=

Model for activity recognition

Epistemic Considerations

Pipeline

Sensor Data

+

Extracted Probabilities from Diaries

=

Model for activity recognition

Semantics

Add Qualitative Data

Positionality

Inherited via human creation

Rigor

Inherited via human creation

Epistemic Considerations

Pipeline

Sensor Data

+

Automatically Extracted Probabilities
from Diaries

=

Model for activity recognition

Epistemic Considerations

Pipeline

Sensor Data

+

Automatically Extracted Probabilities from Diaries

=

Model for activity recognition

Semantics

Add Parameter

Positionality

Unclaimed by human creator(s) of technology

Rigor

Responsibility Unclaimed

Epistemic Considerations

Semantics

Add Qualitative Data

Positionality

Inherited via human creation

Rigor

Inherited via human creation

vs

Semantics

Add Parameter

Positionality

Unclaimed by tech creator

Rigor

Responsibility Unclaimed

Is this a problem?

Positivist stance: No problem!

Same probabilities - same model - no problem!

Invitation

Qualitative data \neq another parameter

Invitation

Reflection

Positionality statements for technology

Engage participants

Checks with originators of text, include them in mean making

Protocols

Checks for consent, data provenance

Qualitative Data make ML human

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Interested?

Collaborators welcome!
Ideas? Hints? Obvious Misunderstandings?

Inspired by:

Subjectivity is a Feature, not a Flaw, A Call to Unsilence the Human Element in
Science - Field & Pownall

Reflexivity in Quantitative Research: A Rationale and Beginners Guide - Jamieson
et al.

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